

COMPARISON OF METERED DOSE INHALER WITH SPACER & NEBULIZATION IN ACUTE ASTHMA EXACERBATIONS IN CHILDREN

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Introduction:

Acute asthma exacerbations in children require immediate and effective bronchodilator treatment. Although nebulization has long served as the predominant method of drug delivery, metered-dose inhalers (MDIs) used in conjunction with spacers have increasingly been recognized as a reliable alternative. This study was conducted to assess and compare the efficacy and safety of MDI therapy with a spacer versus nebulization in the management of acute asthma exacerbations in children.

Materials and Methods:

This prospective comparative study was conducted from February 2025 to January 2026 at a rural tertiary care hospital in South India. A total of 100 children aged 5–15 years with acute asthma exacerbations were included and randomly allocated into two groups: MDI with spacer (n=50) and nebulization (n=50). Baseline demographic and clinical parameters were recorded for all participants. Clinical response was assessed using respiratory rate, oxygen saturation (SpO₂), and clinical asthma score at baseline, and again after 1 hour and 2 hours of treatment. Secondary outcomes included duration of hospital stay, need for additional bronchodilator doses, and occurrence of adverse effects.

Results:

Baseline characteristics were comparable between the two groups ($p > 0.05$). At 1 hour, the MDI group showed significantly better improvement in respiratory rate (26.8 ± 3.5 vs 28.9 ± 3.8), SpO₂ (97.1 ± 1.2 vs 95.8 ± 1.6), and clinical asthma score ($3.2 \pm$

0.9 vs 4.1 ± 1.1) ($p < 0.05$). Overall clinical improvement at 2 hours was higher in the MDI group (84% vs 72%, $p > 0.05$). The duration of hospital stay was significantly shorter (18.4 ± 5.2 vs 24.6 ± 6.1 hours), and fewer patients required additional bronchodilator doses (26% vs 44%) in the MDI group ($p > 0.05$). Adverse effects such as tachycardia and tremors were significantly higher in the nebulization group.

Conclusion:

MDI with spacer is as effective as nebulization and offers advantages including faster clinical improvement, shorter hospital stay, and fewer adverse effects. It can be considered a safe, efficient, and cost-effective alternative in the management of pediatric acute asthma exacerbations.

Keywords:

Acute asthma, children, metered dose inhaler, nebulization, spacer, bronchodilator therapy

INTRODUCTION

Bronchial asthma is one of the most common chronic respiratory disorders affecting children worldwide. It is marked by airway inflammation, bronchial hyperresponsiveness, and reversible airflow obstruction.¹ Children with asthma often have recurrent episodes of wheezing, cough, breathlessness, and chest tightness, especially during acute exacerbations². This condition leads to significant health problems, including increased morbidity, school absenteeism, and greater need for healthcare services, making it an important public health concern. Inhalational therapy remains the cornerstone of asthma management because it delivers medication directly to the airways, providing rapid symptom relief while causing fewer systemic side effects³.

Acute asthma exacerbations in children require prompt and effective bronchodilator therapy to relieve airway blockage and reduce the risk of worsening into respiratory failure. Short-acting β_2 -agonists, such as salbutamol, are the main treatment and are commonly given using either nebulization or a metered dose inhaler (MDI) with a spacer⁴. In emergency settings, nebulization has traditionally been preferred because it is easier to use, particularly in younger children⁵. However, it can

be more expensive, needs electricity, takes longer to administer, and carries a risk of contamination.

Metered dose inhalers with spacers are now widely used as an effective alternative for giving bronchodilators during acute exacerbations. They are portable, generally more cost-effective, and can deliver similar amounts of medication to the lungs when used correctly⁶. Even with these benefits, incorrect inhalation technique is still a major problem. Recent research have found that many pediatric patients make significant errors when using an MDI, and these mistakes can reduce treatment effectiveness and can lead to worse outcomes⁷.

Epidemiologically, asthma affects more than 300 million people worldwide and is the most common chronic disease in children, with increasing trends seen over the past few decades⁸. Global data describes that about 1 in 20 children have severe asthma symptoms⁹. In India, the prevalence of childhood asthma varies widely due to differences in geography, environmental exposures, and study methods, ranging from 2% to 18%, with a pooled prevalence of approximately 7.9% among children¹⁰. Urbanization, air pollution, and socio-economic factors also play an important role in the rising burden of pediatric asthma in the Indian context¹¹.

Several studies have compared the effectiveness of nebulization and metered dose inhaler (MDI) with a spacer for acute asthma treatment, and many report similar clinical outcomes in mild to moderate exacerbations^{12,13}. However, in real-world practice, the choice of therapy may differ due to physician preference, patient age, the severity of the exacerbation, and the availability of resources. Therefore, well-structured comparative studies are still needed in children to assess how well these two modalities work, how practical they are, and what outcomes they lead to in everyday clinical settings. Hence, the present study aims to compare the efficacy of metered dose inhaler with spacer versus nebulization for managing acute asthma exacerbations in children.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present prospective comparative study was conducted from February 2025 to January 2026 at a rural tertiary care hospital in South India. The study enrolled children aged 5–15 years who presented with acute asthma exacerbations to the paediatric outpatient department (OPD) and inpatient department (IPD)

throughout the study period. Demographic parameters, including age, gender, and socioeconomic status, alongside relevant clinical history—such as duration of illness, history of previous asthma episodes, and prior medication use—were recorded systematically using a structured proforma.

A total of 100 children diagnosed with acute asthma exacerbation were included in the study and were randomly allocated into two groups based on the mode of bronchodilator delivery:

- Group 1: Metered Dose Inhaler (MDI) with spacer (n=50)
- Group 2: Nebulization (n=50)

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children aged 5–15 years
- Children diagnosed with acute asthma exacerbation based on clinical features (wheezing, breathlessness, cough, and use of accessory muscles)
- Children with mild to moderate severity of exacerbation
- Children whose parents/guardians provided informed consent

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children with severe or life-threatening asthma requiring immediate intensive care
- Children with underlying chronic respiratory diseases other than asthma (e.g., cystic fibrosis, bronchiectasis)
- Children with congenital heart disease or other systemic illnesses
- Children with known hypersensitivity to β 2-agonists
- Children whose parents/guardians did not provide consent

Study Procedure:

After obtaining informed consent from parents or guardians, all eligible children were clinically assessed, and baseline parameters—including respiratory rate, heart rate, oxygen saturation (SpO₂), and the clinical asthma severity score—were recorded at admission.

Children in Group 1 (MDI with spacer) received salbutamol using a metered dose inhaler with a spacer. The dose was given as 2–4 puffs (100 µg per puff), repeated every 20 minutes for three doses, following the standard protocol.

Children in Group 2 (Nebulization) received salbutamol by nebulization at 0.15 mg/kg per dose, diluted in normal saline, given at similar 20-minute intervals.

Clinical response was assessed at baseline and again at fixed time points 1 hour and 2 hours after treatment. Respiratory rate, wheeze score, use of accessory muscles, oxygen saturation, and overall clinical improvement were recorded at these intervals.

The primary outcome measures were improvement in the clinical asthma score, change in respiratory rate, and improvement in oxygen saturation. Secondary outcomes included the length of hospital stay, whether additional bronchodilator doses were needed, and the occurrence of adverse effects such as tachycardia, tremors, or vomiting.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. Continuous variables such as respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, and clinical scores were presented as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage. The two groups were compared using the independent sample t-test for continuous variables and the chi-square test for categorical variables. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Variable	MDI with Spacer (n=50)	Nebulization (n=50)	p-value
Age (years) (Mean \pm SD)	9.8 \pm 2.6	10.1 \pm 2.4	0.58
Gender			
Male	29 (58%)	27 (54%)	0.68
Female	21 (42%)	23 (46%)	

Variable	MDI with Spacer (n=50)	Nebulization (n=50)	p-value
Socioeconomic Status			0.68
Low	26 (52%)	28 (56%)	
Middle/High	24 (48%)	22 (44%)	

Table 1: Baseline Demographic Characteristics of Study Population

As seen in Table 1, both groups were comparable with respect to age, gender, and socioeconomic status. No statistically significant difference was observed between the two groups ($p>0.05$), indicating appropriate baseline comparability. Independent sample t-test (continuous variables) and Chi-square test (categorical variables) were used to analyse the table.

Parameter	MDI with Spacer (Mean \pm SD)	Nebulization (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
Respiratory Rate (breaths/min)	34.6 \pm 4.2	35.1 \pm 4.5	0.56
Heart Rate (beats/min)	112.4 \pm 10.5	114.2 \pm 9.8	0.39
SpO ₂ (%)	93.2 \pm 2.1	92.8 \pm 2.3	0.34
Clinical Asthma Score	6.8 \pm 1.2	7.0 \pm 1.3	0.41

Table 2: Baseline Clinical Parameters at Admission

As seen in Table 2, baseline clinical parameters including respiratory rate, heart rate, oxygen saturation, and asthma severity score were comparable between both groups. No statistically significant difference was observed ($p>0.05$). Independent sample t-test was used to analyse the table

Parameter	MDI with Spacer (Mean \pm SD)	Nebulization (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
Respiratory Rate	26.8 \pm 3.5	28.9 \pm 3.8	<0.05

Parameter	MDI with Spacer (Mean \pm SD)	Nebulization (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
SpO ₂ (%)	97.1 \pm 1.2	95.8 \pm 1.6	<0.05
Clinical Asthma Score	3.2 \pm 0.9	4.1 \pm 1.1	<0.05

Table 3: Improvement in Clinical Parameters at 1 Hour

As seen in Table 3, children treated with MDI and spacer showed significantly better improvement in respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, and clinical asthma score at 1 hour compared to nebulization ($p < 0.05$). Independent sample t-test was used in the table.

Outcome	MDI with Spacer (n=50)	Nebulization (n=50)	p-value
Improved	42 (84%)	36 (72%)	0.14
Not Improved	8 (16%)	14 (28%)	

Table 4: Overall Clinical Improvement at 2 Hours

As seen in Table 4, a higher proportion of children in the MDI with spacer group showed overall clinical improvement at 2 hours compared to the nebulization group ($p > 0.05$). Chi-square test was used to analyse the table.

Parameter	MDI with Spacer	Nebulization	p-value
Duration of Hospital Stay (hours)	18.4 \pm 5.2	24.6 \pm 6.1	<0.05
Additional Bronchodilator Required	13 (26%)	22 (44%)	0.06

Table 5: Secondary Outcomes – Hospital Stay and Additional Therapy

As seen in Table 5, children in the MDI with spacer group had a significantly shorter duration of hospital stay and required fewer additional bronchodilator doses compared to the nebulization group ($p > 0.05$). Independent sample t-test (continuous variable) and Chi-square test (categorical variable) were used in the table.

Adverse Effect	MDI with Spacer (n=50)	Nebulization (n=50)	p-value
Tachycardia	5 (10%)	14 (28%)	<0.05
Tremors	3 (6%)	11 (22%)	<0.05
Vomiting	2 (4%)	4 (8%)	0.40

Table 6: Adverse Effects Observed in Both Groups

As seen in Table 6, adverse effects such as tachycardia and tremors were significantly more common in the nebulization group compared to the MDI with spacer group ($p < 0.05$). However, vomiting did not show a statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$). Chi-square test was used to analyse the table.

DISCUSSION

The present study compared the effectiveness of a metered dose inhaler (MDI) with a spacer versus nebulization for treating acute asthma exacerbations in children. In both groups, baseline demographic and clinical features were similar, including age (9.8 ± 2.6 vs 10.1 ± 2.4 years; $p = 0.58$), gender distribution, and initial clinical severity scores (6.8 ± 1.2 vs 7.0 ± 1.3 ; $p = 0.41$). Similar results were reported by Chou KJ et al.¹⁴, who found no significant differences between groups in age, sex, or asthma severity at presentation, supporting that the groups were appropriately comparable. Likewise, Mitselou N et al.¹⁵ reported comparable baseline characteristics between the MDI and nebulization groups, further supporting the validity of comparing outcomes between the two treatments.

In the present study, the MDI with spacer group showed significant improvement at 1 hour in clinical parameters, including respiratory rate (26.8 ± 3.5 vs 28.9 ± 3.8), oxygen saturation (97.1 ± 1.2 vs 95.8 ± 1.6), and clinical asthma score

(3.2 ± 0.9 vs 4.1 ± 1.1) ($p < 0.05$). However, earlier studies have reported similar effectiveness between the two treatment options. Roncada C. et al.¹⁶, in a meta-analysis of randomized trials, found no significant difference in respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, or asthma scores between MDI with spacer and nebulization. Benito Fernández J. et al.¹⁷ also reported no significant difference in oxygen saturation and heart rate between the groups. The better results seen in the present study with MDI may be related to more effective drug deposition and correct spacer use.

At the 2-hour time point, the present study also showed a higher proportion of overall clinical improvement in the MDI group (84% vs 72%) with p value greater than 0.05. Similarly, Sugiura K. et al.¹⁸ reported no statistically significant difference in clinical score reduction between the groups (MPIS 3.7 vs 4.3; $p = 0.13$) and no difference in hospitalization rates.

In the present study, we found that the secondary outcomes were better in the MDI group. The hospital stay was significantly shorter (18.4 ± 5.2 vs 24.6 ± 6.1 hours; $p < 0.05$), and fewer children needed extra bronchodilator doses (26% vs 44%; $p > 0.05$). Similar results were reported by Chou KJ et al.¹⁴, who found shorter treatment times in the emergency department with MDI (66 vs 103 minutes; $p < 0.001$). Sugiura K et al.[18] also showed a significantly shorter length of stay with MDI (61 vs 94 minutes; $p < 0.001$). In addition, Goh AE et al.¹⁹ reported less hospital stay and lower cost when MDI was used, which supports the efficiency of MDI-based therapy.

Adverse effects were more common in the nebulization group. In particular, tachycardia (10% vs 28%) and tremors (6% vs 22%) were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$). Vomiting, however, did not differ significantly between the two groups. These findings match those of Chou KJ et al.¹⁴, who reported a higher increase in heart rate and a higher rate of vomiting with nebulization (20% vs 9%; $p < 0.04$). Likewise, Sugiura K et al.¹⁸ found fewer adverse events with MDI, with only 2% experiencing vomiting. Furthermore, a survey by Melethil S et al.²⁰ showed that most clinicians believe nebulization causes more side effects than MDI with a spacer, which supports the safety profile seen in the present study.

Overall, the findings of the present study are consistent with the majority of available literature, which suggests that MDI with spacer is at least as effective as nebulization in the management of acute asthma exacerbations in children. Studies such as those by Delgado A et al.²¹ have also demonstrated comparable efficacy with lower admission rates in the MDI group. Additionally, Graybill C et al.²² reported improved clinical outcomes and reduced follow-up visits with MDI use. Thus, MDI with spacer offers several advantages including shorter treatment duration, reduced hospital stay, fewer adverse effects, and improved cost-effectiveness, making it a viable alternative to nebulization in pediatric acute asthma management.

Overall, the results of the present study are in keeping with most of the existing literature, which indicates that MDI delivered with a spacer is at least as effective as nebulization for the management of acute asthma exacerbations in children. Evidence from studies such as those conducted by Delgado A et al.²¹ has further shown similar therapeutic efficacy alongside lower admission rates in the MDI group. In addition, Graybill C et al.²² reported better clinical outcomes and fewer follow-up visits associated with MDI use. Taken together, these findings suggest that MDI with spacer provides multiple advantages, including a reduced treatment duration, decreased likelihood of hospital admission, fewer adverse effects, and improved cost-effectiveness, thereby supporting its use as a practical and viable alternative to nebulization in pediatric acute asthma management.

CONCLUSION

MDI with spacer is as effective as nebulization in the management of acute asthma exacerbations in children and demonstrates advantages such as shorter hospital stay and fewer adverse effects. Hence, MDI with spacer can be considered a safe, efficient, and cost-effective alternative to nebulization in clinical practice.

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ABBREVIATIONS

MDI: Metered Dose Inhaler; OPD: Outpatient Department; IPD: Inpatient Department; SpO₂: Peripheral Oxygen Saturation; SD: Standard Deviation; SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences; β 2-agonist: Beta-2 Agonist; RR: Respiratory Rate; p-value: Probability value.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical Committee approval was obtained from the Institute viz No. P/2025/82. The study protocol involving human participants was approved in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors made substantial contributions to the conception and design of the study, the acquisition of data, the analysis and interpretation of the data, and the drafting of the manuscript. The corresponding author played a primary role in the supervision of the study, the preparation of the manuscript, the critical revision of the content, and the final approval of the version to be submitted. In addition, all authors reviewed the final manuscript carefully and approved it for submission.

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Availability of data and materials

The anonymized dataset generated and analysed during the current study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Consent for publication

Written informed consent for publication of anonymized clinical data was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participating children prior to enrolment in the study.

DECLARATION OF GENERATIVE AI AND AI-ASSISTED TECHNOLOGIES IN THE WRITING PROCESS

The authors declare that generative AI and/or AI-assisted technologies were used only for language refinement, grammar correction, formatting assistance, and improvement of readability during manuscript preparation. The authors take full responsibility for the content of the manuscript.

Competing Interests:

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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